

**TECHNICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS
INFLUENCING IMPLEMENTATION OF QUALITY ASSURANCE
AND STANDARDS POLICY IN KENYAN PUBLIC
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KEIYO SUB COUNTY OF
ELGEIYO MARAKWET COUNTY, KENYA**

**Wambua Kyalo Benjamin¹ⁱ,
Kigen Viola J.²,
Khaemba Ongeti³**

¹Senior Lecturer, Department of Educational Management and Policy studies,
School of Education, Moi University, P.O Box 3900-30100, Eldoret Kenya

²Graduate Student, Department of Educational Management and Policy studies
School of Education, Moi University, P.O Box 3900-30100, Eldoret Kenya

³Associate Professor, Department of Curriculum, Instruction and Media
School of Education, Moi University, P.O Box 3900-30100, Eldoret Kenya

Abstract:

There is growing concern by various stakeholders about the declining student achievement and teacher performance highlighted by strong media publicity and frequently acknowledged in educational analysis in Kenyan schools. This paper examined technical and environmental factors influencing the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Kenya. The study was based on the Effective Schools Theory. This study employed a descriptive research design as it involved gathering data as well as describes events. The study was carried out in Keiyo Sub County, in Elgeiyo Marakwet County. The Keiyo Sub County has 38 public secondary schools. In each of these schools, there are six officers concerned with Quality Assurance and Standards. Thus, in total, there were 38 schools of which five heads of departments and one principal/head teacher was selected to get 228 respondents in charge of quality in the whole Sub-County. Both probability and non-probability sampling designs were employed to determine sample size. Purposive sampling was used to select five heads of departments and one principal/head teacher.

ⁱ Correspondence: email kyalowmb44@gmail.com

Data were collected using closed and open-ended questionnaire. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The study established that technical factors positively affected the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards(QAS) policy in public secondary schools were; the level of training, staffing level of the QAS officers, innovativeness of the QAS and means of transport used by the QAS officers. The surroundings of the school, weather conditions and the socio-economic activities of teachers influence the implementation of QAS policy. The location of QAS officers and accessibility of school does not influence the implementation of QAS policy.

Keywords: technical, environmental, quality, assurance, standards

1. Introduction

Education is central to economic and political development of any country, and vital to competitiveness in an increasingly globalizing knowledge society. In any group of individuals performing a certain task towards a set objective supervision has to be in place to ensure that the desired objective is achieved (Khawas, Pietro-Jurand, & Nielsen, 2008). Quality assurance in education is a systematic management and assessment procedures adopted by education institutions and systems in order to monitor performance against objectives, and to ensure achievements of quality outputs and quality improvements (Harman, 2000).

In the American system of education, the purpose of supervisions (as it applies to the relationship between a school leader and school teachers) is to assist in creating a tone; A tone of respect, a tone of inclusion, a tone of caring, a tone of professionalism, a tone of reflection, a tone of doing it better and a tone of celebration to assist in crafting a vision, to assist in collaboration on goals leading to the vision and to assist in assessing improvement (Glickman, 1995).

The West African Education Ordinance covering the colonies of Lagos, Sierra Leone and the Gambia was promulgated in 1882. This provides for establishment of school inspectorate services (Omorieg, 2004). The constitution thereby gives this authority to the Ministry of Education to ensure quality control of the educational system through the inspection of schools and institutions as well as to appoint inspectors to conduct inspections and report on the nature of instruction and examination in schools. The inspectors also referred to superintendents were

authoritarian, they harassed teachers and terrorized schools, consequently the image of the inspector became uncomplimentary one (Omoriegie, 2004).

Quality is at the heart of most education policy agendas and improving quality is probably the most important task facing many educational institutions. With this concern has also come an increasing accountability demand. There is growing concern by various stakeholders about the declining student achievement and teacher performance highlighted by strong media publicity and frequently acknowledged in educational analysis in Kenyan schools (Odhiambo, 2008).

In a study entitled *Elusive Search for Quality Education: The Case of Quality Assurance and Teacher Accountability in Kenya* (2008), the government is faulted for incompetence and unfocused approach to education. Odhiambo (2008) asserts that, basically, the underlying cause of poor quality education in Kenya's schools is not the performance of teachers per se but deeply rooted in management practices and government policies which have to change if this dream is to be realized. However, on immediate measures, Odhiambo (2008), argues that there is urgent need to undertake comprehensive evaluation of teachers in public schools, simply because their professional performance cannot be separated from their pupil's outcome. The Kenya Education Sector Support Programme (KESSP) report (2005-2010), supports effective monitoring of curriculum delivery in schools to ensure teacher effectiveness which is a mandate under the Directorate of Quality Assurance and Standards (DQAS) and is performed by QASOs.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Koech (2008), reports that parents, because of the numerous school strikes, have expressed major concerns about mismanagement of schools and poor performance on national examinations. Opinion is divided on where the focus should be to mitigate the deteriorating quality of education. It has been observed that despite the provision for continuous Quality Assurance and Standards assessments little seem to be accruing from the process. This study therefore, seeks to establish technical and environmental factors that affect the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards mechanisms employed in public secondary schools.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to;

1. Examine the Implementation of Quality assurance standards in public secondary schools
2. Examine technical factors that influence the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Kenya.
3. Explore the environmental factors that affect the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Kenya.

1.3 Null Hypothesis

Ho₁: Technical factors do not significantly influence the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Kenya.

Ho₂: The environmental factors do not significantly affect the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Kenya.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The study was based on the Effective Schools Theory by Lezotte (2001). According to Lezotte (2001), an effective school is measured in terms of student achievement and demonstrates evidence of quality and equity. After a series of studies, Lezotte (2001) came up with seven correlates of effective schools – among them are strong instructional leadership, clear and focused mission, safe and orderly schools, climate of high expectations for success, frequent monitoring of student progress, positive home–school relations, and opportunity to learn/time on task.

This study explored technical and environmental factors influencing the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Keiyo Sub County. In relation to the study, the theory was important in guiding the definition and conceptualization of the relationship among the key variables under observation. For instance, identifying how such factors as the availability of books and other learning resources, qualification of the teacher, frequency of school inspection, student' social-cultural background, teacher-student ratio, among others, influence Implementation of quality assurance and standards in schools.

2.1.1 Technical factors that influence the Implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

The supervision of instruction is by design a developmental process with the main purpose of improving the instructional program, generally and teaching, specifically.

Only when this process is carefully planned and executed can success be assured. The supervisory function is best utilized as a continuous process rather than one that responds only to personnel problems. Administrators with supervisory responsibility have the opportunity to have tremendous influence on the school program and help ensure the benefits of a strong program of instruction for children. Despite these reforms, this sector of education continues to experience problems in achievement of its goals.

2.1.2 Environmental factors that affect the Implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

A school has many stakeholders including others who have less or no knowledge of school activities. Quality assurance in learning institutions has become not only an institutional issue but also a global one. Schools throughout the world today are focusing special attention on designing and implementing new quality assurance mechanisms and systems in order to ensure that students receive high quality and relevant education. Quality assurance in education can be defined as a systematic management and assessment procedures adopted by education institutions and systems in order to monitor performance against objectives, and to ensure achievements of quality outputs and improvements (Harman, 2000).

According to Manakin (2010), quality assurance is a planned and systematic review process of an institution or program to determine whether or not acceptable standards of education, scholarship, and infrastructure are being met, maintained and enhanced. Essentially, quality assurance systems aim to provide appropriate evidence to substantiate claims made about quality and so to enable key stakeholders to have confidence about the management of quality and the level of outcome achieved. Essentially, quality assurance systems aim to provide appropriate evidence to substantiate claims made about quality and so to enable key stakeholders to have confidence about the management of quality and the level of outcome achieved. Quality is at the heart of education and what takes place in classrooms and other learning environments is fundamentally important to the future well-being of young people and adults (Manakin, 2010).

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The independent variables of the study consist of the obstacles faced by QASOs in supervision of the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary school. These include technical and environmental factors, which influences

effectiveness of the implementation of the curriculum that was considered as the independent variable of the study. The study identified these factors by assuming the conceptual framework presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

2.3 Summary of Literature

Developing standards in education and maintaining the desired quality remains a major challenge across education systems throughout the world. Quality in education is perceived as the degree to which education can be said to be of high standard, satisfies basic learning needs, and enriches the lives of learners and their overall experience of living (UNESCO, 2000). During the World Education Forum held in Dakar in 2000, participants committed themselves to improving the quality of all aspects of education. The delegates concluded that quality is at the heart of education and is one of the key goals in achievement of Education for All (EFA). The role and character of standards and quality assurance varies from country to country. The purpose of quality assurance is to identify strengths and weaknesses at schools and wider institutional level so that a school may maintain effective school management systems, improve the quality of education provided and raise the educational standards achieved by pupils (Republic of Kenya, 2012).

The overall policy of the government of Kenya is to achieve education for all. The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in quality and efficiency at all levels of education. The ultimate goal is to develop an all inclusive and quality education that is accessible and relevant to all Kenyans. This is guided by the understanding that good education can contribute significantly to economic growth, improved employment prospects and income generating opportunities.

The government policy also entails allowing a broad based participation in the provision of education with all stakeholders taking responsibility for planning and

implementation. In tandem with this policy is the decentralization of decision making and resource management at lower level structures of the ministry. The Constitution of Kenya (Republic of Kenya, 2010) provides for two levels of government: the central government and 47 county governments which are distinct yet interdependent. Education policies are formulated by the National Education Board and executed by the County Education Boards. Despite these glaring similarities, quality assurance and standards officers in the education sector have not fully integrated participatory monitoring and evaluation approaches in order to implement Quality Assurance and Standards policy.

Literature reviewed in this chapter has shown the important role played by Quality Assurance and Standards Officers in school supervision and the quality has always been an issue of concern in education. The introduction of free secondary education introduced new challenges that require school inspectors to be more vigilant to ensure that quality of secondary education is not compromised. In the present result-based educational economy, quality remains a critical subject considering the value of financial input by various stakeholders against constrained resources.

QASO roles seems to lack the value of being perceived as important, objective and focused on the issues most important in improving performance by the teachers as implementers of the curriculum. The poorly motivated and not that qualified principal, can do process control by making periodical checks to ensure that they are continuously operating within certain pre-established tolerances to prevent defects by making timely adjustments. This calls for the improvement of the internal school supervision processes. Previous studies on quality of primary education have concentrated on the challenges faced by head teachers in school management, while the obstacles faced by QASOs in supervision of curriculum instruction have not been documented.

However, the studies did not assess the views of the teachers on the contributions of the QASOs in curriculum implementation. The studies did not outline the areas in which the QASOs had contributed positively in enhancing proper curriculum implementation. The studies had not assessed the problems facing the co-operation of the QASOs and teachers in curriculum implementation. Hence, this study assessed the contribution of the QASO in curriculum implementation as well as the problems facing the co-operation of the QASO with teachers. The literature indicates that training and quality of personnel do not guarantee improved supervisory practices unless such are accompanied by total commitment, dedication and change of attitude by both QASOS and teachers towards each other but there was no any elaboration on what to be done to guarantee improved supervision. This study therefore sought to fill

this research gap by investigating the factors influencing QASOs in implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design as it involved gathering data as well as describes events (Orodho, 2009). Descriptive methods are widely used to obtain data useful in evaluating present practices and providing for decision. This method was appropriate as it gives a detailed description of technical and environmental factors that influence the implementation of quality assurance and standards among public secondary schools which can be generalized to other parts of Kenya.

3.2 Study Area

The study was carried out in Keiyo Sub County, in Elgeiyo Marakwet County. The Sub-County is divided into five administrative divisions namely; Chepkorio, Kamariny, Soy, Metkei and Tambach. The bordering Counties are; Koibatek, Baringo, Eldoret East and Marakwet. The County has 38 public and 1 private secondary schools. Out of the 38 public secondary schools 8, are boys boarding 10 are girls boarding and 20 are mixed schools. The total student enrollment is 11,362 of which 5,449 are boys while 5913 are girls. The Sub-County has 473 teachers. The Sub- County has 13 education zones (DEO'S Statistics, 2009). It has been observed by the researcher that Keiyo Sub County has been performing poorly in academics especially at secondary schools. This is despite the fact that there is continuous assessment of schools by the Quality Assurance and Standards officers. The Sub- County is also least studied, especially on the subject matter and therefore, provides a viable ground for scientific investigation.

3.3 Target Population

The target population comprised of 38 principals and 190 heads of departments each from science, language, humanities, mathematics and applied and technical subjects. The respondents were selected because they constitute the school management team alongside other stakeholders, and they are also implementers of all school policies. For instance, they are vested with the responsibility of ensuring Quality Assurance and Standards of their respective schools. They are also the ones that either fill the Quality Assurance and Standards forms or talk to Quality Assurance and Standards officers on behalf of the rest of the stakeholders in their respective schools. It's therefore clear that

by the nature of their daily administrative duties, they are the best placed to provide a clear picture of the actual situation on the ground with regard to the topic of study.

3.4 Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

There were 38 schools of which five heads of departments and one principal/head teacher was selected to get 228 respondents in charge of quality in the whole Sub-County. Purposive sampling was used to select five heads of departments and one principal/head teacher. Since, heads of departments and one principal/head teacher were more informed and have a similar characteristic that is near equal level of education, therefore more homogeneous than when teachers have different levels of education, included as part of the sample.

Table 1: Sampling Frame

Respondent	Target population	Sample size
Head teacher	38	38
Head of Science Department	38	38
Head of Language Department	38	38
Head of Department- humanities	38	38
Head of Department-Mathematics	38	38
Head of Department-Applied and Technical Subjects	38	38
Total	228	228

3.5 Data Collection Instruments

Reliable data depends on the precision of the research instruments used. Therefore, to have reliable data, suitable instruments were necessary to provide high accuracy for generalization. This study used questionnaires to collect information from the respondents. The use of questionnaires is suitable for obtaining relevant information for the study as stated by Mugenda, (2008). It enabled collection of information from various schools over a short period of time. According to Kothari (2008), questionnaires are usually free from the interview bias as the answers are in respondent own words.

3.6 Data Analysis Techniques

The reason for carrying out data processing is to prepare raw data for statistical analysis and presentation. After all data was collected, the researcher conducted data cleaning, which involved identification of incomplete or inaccurate responses, which were corrected to improve the quality of the responses. After data cleaning, the data was coded and entered in the computer for analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. This research yielded both qualitative and quantitative

data. Qualitative data was analyzed qualitatively using content analysis based on analysis of meanings and implications emanating from respondents' information and documented data. On the other hand, quantitative data was analyzed using Pearson product moment.

The Pearson correlation analysis was used to establish the relationship between two variables in a linear fashion. Pearson product moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine relationship between technical and environmental factors and implementation of quality assurance and standards policy in Kenya public secondary schools in Keiyo Sub- County. It was appropriate to use the technique for interval and ratio-scaled variables and determine the relationship between one variable and another.

4. Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1 Summary of Findings

4.1.1 Implementation of Quality assurance standards in public secondary schools

The respondents were requested to rate the implementation of quality assurance standards in public secondary schools. Most of the respondents 76 (47.2%) disagree that the Quality Assurance and Standards officers (QAS) are always on time, with 22.4% agreed, 14.9% undecided and 10.6% strongly disagreed. This indicated that most of the respondents 57.8% disagreed that the QAS officers were always there on time.

Most of the respondents 84 (52.2%) agreed that the QAS officers do not meet the number of visits they are supposed to make to each school, with 21.7% disagree and 19.9% undecided. This indicated that majority of the respondents 58.4% agreed that QAS officers do not meet the number of visits they are supposed to make to each school. At least 42.9% of the respondents disagreed that QAS process remains an administrative (concerns the Heads of departments (HoDs) and principals only) issues at the school level, with 31.7% strongly disagree and 20.5% agreed. This implies that most of the respondents 120 (74.6%) disagreed that QAS process remains an administrative concern for both the Heads of Departments and principals' issues at the school level.

Wambua Kyalo Benjamin, Kigen Viola J., Khaemba Ongeti
 TECHNICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS INFLUENCING IMPLEMENTATION OF QUALITY
 ASSURANCE AND STANDARDS POLICY IN KENYAN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KEIYO SUB
 COUNTY OF ELGEIYO MARAKWET COUNTY, KENYA

Table 2: Implementation of Quality assurance and standards in public secondary schools

Statement	SA		A		UD		D		SD	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
The QAS officers are always on time	8	5.0	36	22.4	24	14.9	76	47.2	17	10.6
The QAS officers do not meet the number of visits they are supposed to for each school.	10	6.2	84	52.2	32	19.9	35	21.7		
The QAS process remains an administrative issue			33	20.5	8	5.0	69	42.9	51	31.7
There is no feedback on the information we give on QAS in our school	11	6.8	27	16.8	24	14.9	68	42.2	31	19.3
The QAS is a government policy	10	6.2	102	63.4	24	14.9	9	5.6	16	9.9
The education officers in the County can decide whether to carry out the QAS or not	8	5.0	82	50.9	24	14.9	28	17.4	19	11.8
Information on QAS has been used to improve my school conditions	6	3.7	95	59.0	16	9.9	28	17.4	16	9.9
The current tools used in QAS are outdated	4	2.5	13	8.1	36	22.4	69	42.9	39	24.2
Those concerned with QAS in school are well trained and have control over the process			93	57.8	33	20.5	28	17.4	7	4.3

SA=strongly agree (5). A=agree (4); UD=undecided (3); D=disagree (2); SD=strongly disagree (1)

Most of the respondents 68 (42.2%) disagree that there is no feedback on the information given on QAS in our school, with 19.3% strongly disagreed, 14.9% undecided and 16.8% agreed. This indicated that most of the respondents 61.5% disagreed that there is no feedback on the information given on QAS in our school. Majority 82 (50.9%) of the respondents agreed that education officers in the County decides whether to carry out the QAS process in a school or not, with 17.4% disagreed, 14.9% undecided and 11.8% strongly disagreed. This implies that most of the respondents 55.9% agreed that education officers in the County were the ones to decide whether to carry out the QAS process in a school or not. Most of the respondents 95 (59%) agreed that the information from QAS had been used to improve school conditions with 17.4% disagree, 9.9% undecided and strongly disagreed. This indicated that majority of the respondents 62.7% agreed that information on QAS had been used to improve school conditions.

Most of the respondents 69 (42.9%) disagreed that the current tools used in QAS were outdated with 24.2% strongly disagree, 22.2% undecided and 8.1% agreed. This

indicated that majority of the respondents 108 (67.1%) disagreed that current tools used in QAS were outdated. Majority 93 (57.8%) of the respondents agreed that those concerned with QAS were well trained and had control over the process, with 20.5% undecided, 17.4% disagreed and 4.3% strongly disagree and 20.5% agreed. This implies that most of the respondents 78.3% agreed that those concerned with QAS were well trained and had control over the process. Most of the respondents 102 (63.4%) agreed that QAS was a government policy, with 14.9% undecided, 17.4% disagree, 9.9% strongly disagreed and 6.2% strongly agreed. This indicated that majority of the respondents 69.6% agreed that QAS was a government policy.

From the study, the implementation of quality assurance standards in public secondary schools was rated differently by respondents. Most of the respondents disagree that the QAS officers were always on time, QAS process remained an administrative concern for both the HoDs and principals at the school level, there was no feedback on the information given on QAS in school and current tools used in QAS were outdated.

4.1.2 Technical factors influencing the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

The respondents were required to rate the extent they agree or disagree with statements relating to the technical factors that influence the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools using a five point Likert scale. From each statement, explaining the technical factors was computed using frequencies and percentages as shown in Table 2.

Most 65 (40.4%) of the respondents agree that the level of training of the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 39.1% strongly agreed 8.1% undecided and 7.5% strongly disagreed. This indicated that most 79.5% of the respondents agreed that the level of training of the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy. Majority 80 (49.7%) of the respondents agreed that the staffing level of the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 40.4% strongly agreed 7.5% strongly disagreed and 2.5% were undecided. This implies that most 90.1% of the respondents agreed that the staffing level of the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy.

Most 67(41.6%) of the respondents agreed that the innovativeness of the QAS influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 32.9% strongly agreed and 5% disagreed and 20.5% were undecided. This implies that most of the respondents 74.5% agreed that the innovativeness of the QAS influence the level of implementation

of QAS policy. Majority 75 (46.6%) of the respondents agree that means of transport used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 17.4% agreed, 18.6% disagreed and 13% were undecided. This indicated that most of the respondents 64% agreed that the means of transport used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy.

Table 2: Technical factors that influences the implementation of
 Quality Assurance and Standards policy

Statement	SA		A		UD		D		SD	
	Freq	%								
The level of training of the QAS officers	63	39.1	65	40.4	13	8.1	8	5.0	12	7.5
The staffing level of the QAS officers	65	40.4	80	49.7	4	2.5			12	7.5
The innovativeness of the QAS	53	32.9	67	41.6	33	20.5	8	5.0		
The means of transport used by the QAS officers	28	17.4	75	46.6	21	13.0	30	18.6	7	4.3
The number of subjects handled by the QAS officers	45	28.0	89	55.3	7	4.3	12	7.5	8	5.0
The area of jurisdiction of the QAS	73	45.3	61	37.9	12	7.5	8	5.0	7	4.3
Availability of financial resources	45	28.0	76	47.2	12	7.5	12	7.5	16	9.9
Lack of feedback in the process of QAS	42	26.1	72	44.7	15	9.3	12	7.5	20	12.4
The methods used by the QAS officers	22	13.7	100	62.1	8	5.0	28	17.4	3	1.9

SA=strongly agree (5). A=agree (4); UD=undecided (3); D=disagree (2); SD=strongly disagree (1)

Most 89 (55.3%) of the respondents agree that the number of subjects handled by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 28% strongly agreed 7.5% disagreed and 4.3% were undecided. This indicated that most 83.3% of the respondents agreed that the number of subjects handled by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy. Majority 73 (45.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed that the area of jurisdiction of the QAS influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 37.9% agreed 7.5% were undecided and 5% disagreed. This implies that most 83.2% of the respondents agreed that the area of jurisdiction of the QAS influence the level of implementation of QAS policy.

Most 76(47.2%) of the respondents agreed that the availability of financial resources influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 28% strongly agreed and 7.5% disagreed and were undecided. This implies that most of the respondents 75.2% agreed that the innovativeness of the QAS influence the level of

implementation of QAS policy. Majority 72 (44.7%) of the respondents agree that lack of feedback in the process of QAS influences the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 26.1% strongly agreed, 12.4% strongly disagreed and 9.3% were undecided. This indicated that most 70.8% of the respondents agreed that that lack of feedback in the process of QAS influences the level of implementation of QAS policy.

Majority 100 (62.1%) of the respondents agree that methods used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 13.7% strongly agreed, 17.4% disagreed and 5% were undecided. This indicated that most 75.8% of the respondents agreed that methods used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy. From the study, most of the respondents agree that the level of training, staffing level of the QAS officers, innovativeness of the QAS and means of transport used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy. The number of subjects handled by the QAS officers, area of jurisdiction, availability of financial resources and lack of feedback in the process of QAS and methods used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy.

Training of QASOs is important especially on public relations. This is because the QASOs have in the past been accused of being cruel to teachers. For example, Wanjohi (2005) reported that in the past most inspectors were autocratic and authoritarian who always insisted on maintenance and observance of departmental rules, and that whenever they visited schools, they focused on fault-finding instead of advising and encouraging teachers.

Wanjohi (2005) further states that, there was a time when the mention of “school inspector” was enough to make teachers faint. The officials caused terror as they looked for teachers’ mistakes. They were known of storming in to schools where they harassed, victimized and scared teachers by threatening to write negative reports about them. As a result of the mistrust teachers had of the inspectors, many teachers viewed the inspectors’ role with a lot of fear, suspicion and hostility. Wanjohi (2005) contends that teachers perceive inspectors as faultfinders who are only interested in reporting them to the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology instead of giving them advice to enable them improve their teaching techniques. This results in a poor relationship between them and the inspectors.

4.1.3 Pearson Correlation on the influence of Technical factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

Pearson moment correlation was used to show the relationship between technical factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy. There was a

positive influence of technical factors on implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy [$r = .676$, $n = 161$, $p < .05$], as shown in Table 3. This indicated that technical factors influenced the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Keiyo Sub County positively.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation on the influence of Technical factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

		Implementation	Technical
Implementation	Pearson Correlation	1	.676**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Technical	Pearson Correlation	.676**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

N=161

The findings agree with Kinayia (2010) that the Quality Assurance and Standards Officers and head teachers faced many problems in their job such as inaccessible schools, resistance from teachers, inadequate personnel, hostile environment and poor communication.

4.1.4 Environmental factors influencing the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

The third objective of the study was to establish the influence environmental factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Keiyo Sub County. This was established using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics involved the use of frequencies and percentage. The statements used to explain environmental factors were computed to create a variable and subjected to inferential analysis. The inferential statistics involved the use of Pearson correlation coefficient.

4.1.5 Environmental factors

The respondents were required to rate the extent they agree or disagree with statements relating to the environmental factors that influence the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools using a five point Likert scale. From each statement explaining the environmental factors, was computed using frequencies and percentages as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Environmental factors that affects the implementation of
 Quality Assurance and Standards policy

Statement	SA		A		UD		D		SD	
	Freq	%								
The location of QAS officers	16	9.9	43	26.7	20	12.4	68	42.2	14	8.7
The surrounding of the school	17	10.6	67	41.6	8	5.0	48	29.8	21	13.0
Topography	18	11.2	50	31.1	24	14.9	45	28.0	24	14.9
Socio economic activities of teachers	26	16.1	64	39.8	8	5.0	43	26.7	20	12.4
Weather conditions	34	21.1	84	52.2	8	5.0	16	9.9	19	11.8
Accessibility of school			12	7.5	32	19.9	52	32.3	65	40.4

SA-strongly agree (5). A=agree (4); UD=undecided (3); D=disagree (2); SD=strongly disagree (1)

Most 68 (42.2%) of the respondents disagree that the location of QAS officers influences the level of implementation of QAS policy, with 26.7% agreed, 12.4% undecided and 8.7% strongly disagreed. This indicated that most 50.9% of the respondents disagreed that the location of QAS officers influences the level of implementation of QAS policy. Majority 67(41,6%) of the respondents agreed that the surrounding of the school influence the implementation of QAS policy, with 29.8% disagreed, 13% strongly disagreed, while 10.6% strongly agreed and 5% were undecided. This implies that most 52.2% of the respondents agreed that the surrounding of the school influence the implementation of QAS policy.

Most 84(52.2%) of the respondents agreed that weather conditions influence the implementation of QAS policy, with 21.1% strongly agreed, 11.8% strongly disagreed, 9.9% disagreed and 5% were undecided. This implies that most of the respondents 73.3% agreed that the weather conditions influence the implementation of QAS policy. Majority 65 (40.4%) of the respondents strongly disagree that accessibility of school influences the implementation of QAS policy, with 7.5% agreed, 32.3% disagreed and 19.9% were undecided. This indicated that most of the respondents 72.7% disagreed that accessibility of school influences the implementation of QAS policy.

At least 50 (31.1%) of the respondents agree that topography influences the implementation of QAS policy, with 11.2% strongly agreed 28% disagreed, 14.9% strongly disagreed and undecided. However, 64 (39.8%) of the respondents agreed that socio economic activities of teachers influence the implementation of QAS policy, with 16.1% strongly agreed 26.7% disagreed and 12.4% strongly disagreed and 5% were undecided. This implies that most 55.9% of the respondents agreed that the socio-economic activities of teachers influence the implementation of QAS policy.

From the study, most of the respondents disagree that the location of QAS officers and accessibility of school influences the implementation of QAS policy. Majority of the respondents agreed that the surrounding of the school, weather conditions and the socio-economic activities of teachers influence the implementation of QAS policy.

4.1.6 Pearson Correlation on the influence of Environmental factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

Pearson moment correlation was used to show the relationship between environmental factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy. There was a positive influence of environmental factors on implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy [$r = .764$, $n=161$, $p<.05$], as shown in Table 5. This indicated that environmental factors influenced the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools in Keiyo Sub County positively.

Table 5: Pearson Correlation on the influence of Environmental factors on the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy

		Implementation	Environmental
Implementation	Pearson Correlation	1	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Environmental	Pearson Correlation	.764**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

N=161

5. Conclusions

Technical factors positively affected the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy in public secondary schools were; the level of training, staffing level of the QAS officers, innovativeness of the QAS and means of transport used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy. The number of subjects handled by the QAS officers, area of jurisdiction, availability of financial resources and lack of feedback in the process of QAS and methods used by the QAS officers influence the level of implementation of QAS policy.

The environmental factors influenced the implementation of Quality Assurance and Standards policy positively. The surroundings of the school, weather conditions and the socio-economic activities of teachers influence the implementation of QAS

policy. The location of QAS officers and accessibility of school does not influence the implementation of QAS policy.

6. Recommendations

This study found out that internal school QASO lacked the requisite training. Therefore, it is the recommendations of this study that;

1. QASO should be inducted by organizing capacity building training to enhance their knowledge and skills on quality management in education.
2. QASOs should visit schools more frequently for supervision and where possible have follow-up mechanisms in order to ensure that their recommendations are implemented.

References

1. Constitution of Kenya (2010). *Laws of Kenya*. Revised Edition 2010. Nairobi: Government Printing Press.
2. El-Khawas, E.R. DePietro-Jurand, & L. Holm-Nielsen. (2008). "Quality Assurance in Higher Education: Recent Progress; Challenges Ahead." Prepared for UNESCO World Conference on Higher Education, Paris:
3. Glickman, H (1995). *Ethnic Conflict and Democratizations; African Studies Associations Press*
4. Harman, G. (2000). *Quality Assurance in Higher Education; Bangkok: Ministry of University Affairs and UNESCO PROAP*
5. Kinayia, D. (2010). *Secondary School Teachers' Perceptions towards Supervision by Quality Assurance and Standards Officers in Narok County Kenya, M.ed Thesis University of Nairobi.*
6. Kipkoech, L. & Kyalo, B. (2010). Management challenges facing implementation of free primary education in Kenya: A case of Keiyo Sub County. *Journal of educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 2(5): 71-76.
7. Koech, P.K. (2008). *Parent-Teacher Partnerships For Enhancing Pre-School Children's Education in Uasin Gishu District, Kenya (2008) (PhD Thesis)*. Mount Kenya University
8. Kothari, C.R. (2008). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. New Delhi: Wishwa Prakashan.

9. Lezotte, L. (2001). *Correlates of Effective Schools: The first and second generation*. Okemos. Effective Schools Products Ltd: MI.
10. Mugenda A.G. (2008). *Research Methods; Quantitative and Qualitative approaches*. Nairobi: Nairobi Act Press.
11. Odhiambo, G. (2008). Elusive Search for Quality Education; The Case of quality assurance and teacher accountability. *International journal of educational management*, 22: 117-131
12. Omoregie. S.B. (2004). *My Teaching*. London; Longman Publisher
13. Orodho JA (2009). *Elements of Education and Social Science Research Methods*; Maseno: Kanezja Publisher. 2nd edition, ISBN: 978-9966-7350-1-1
14. Republic of Kenya (2012a). *Sessional Paper No.14 of 2012 on realigning education and training to the Constitution of Kenya 2010 and Vision 2030 and beyond*. Ministry of Education Science and Technology. Nairobi: Government Printers.
15. Republic of Kenya/UNICEF (2012). *Education for All (EFA) End of Decade Assessment (2001-2010)*. Ministry of Education and UNICEF. Nairobi: Government Printers.
16. UNESCO. (2000). *The Dakar Framework For Action*. Paris: UNESCO.
17. Wanjohi, S. M. (2005). *Teachers and principals attitude towards school inspection in Kenyas Nyandarua Sub County*. Unpublished Thesis, Njoro: Egerton University.

Wambua Kyalo Benjamin, Kigen Viola J., Khaemba Ongeti
TECHNICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS INFLUENCING IMPLEMENTATION OF QUALITY
ASSURANCE AND STANDARDS POLICY IN KENYAN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KEIYO SUB
COUNTY OF ELGEIYO MARAKWET COUNTY, KENYA

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](#).